

TECHNOLOGICAL INNOVATIONS AND AI IN LANGUAGE LEARNING AND COMMUNICATION

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15486544>

Annotation: When we talk about modern classes and teaching, we cannot imagine it without Ai powered tools. They have already become an essential part of our modern world. It is becoming more and more popular to use Ai tools in ay sphere including teaching and learning sphere as it provides tons of benefits such as saving our time, creating something in a more creative way, completing tasks and assignments in a seconds and even get a real time feedback. The article considers the positive sides of using innovations in an educational sphere.

Key words: AI, education, AI-powered tools, challenges, benefits, feedback, learning languages, simulation.

INTRODUCTION

Nowadays we can witness that most of students and teachers use innovations, AI-tools in almost each situation and they obviously become the part of everyone's daily routine. The students use online platforms for far more purposes rather than teachers. For instance the apps are used by students for doing assignments, learning new languages, making international friends, checking their projects with instant feedback, gather more ideas and information about specific topic and etc. whereas the teachers can use them for organizing creative and effective

lesson plan by avoiding the traditional method of teaching. Thus, if innovations and AI-platforms are used in a right way, they are a powerful tool for everyone.

AI IN LEARNING

AI isn't our dream anymore, it isn't a thing that is beyond our dreams and thought. It exists, it is with us and we can always use AI tools in any situation. If we talk about the impact of AI in education system, AI-powered tools are both used in teaching and learning as well. Teachers use them in order to conduct their lesson in an effective and enjoyable way, whilst they are used by students to complete their assignments on time with feedback and etc (M. Miller).

AI-powered tools support learners and professors in many ways. If we turn our attention to the benefits of it, we can see how influential and effective AI is for us.

Firstly, AI is a key of future education and modern classrooms. Via augmented reality and virtual reality, with the help of special equipments (glasses), students can explore some kind of places, historic monuments and etc by staying at class. This is called augmented reality, when AI-powered tools show the image of a particular place in real time, whilst virtual reality it is when because of simulation the students think that they are in for example ancient Greece and start exploring those times. Virtual reality is far better than augmented one, as simulation allows students not only become part of something, but also feel that place, the students can even participate in operations via wearing special glasses, or they can explore caves, oceans and so on.

The next benefit can be automated grading and feedback. This means that students can send their works, assignments to special sites, and AI will check them all at once students send them. After checking, the students are given real time feedback for their work, so they work on their mistakes, weaknesses and improve their skills. This method of using AI is really good for language learners as they can send even their speaking tasks to special online platforms. And AI will check even their pronunciation as well.

Moreover, in terms of data-driven insights in teaching with AI plays a crucial role in improving teaching process. Most of teachers for example conduct their lessons by creating online games in special platforms. This kind of games can rate the students' progress and show their weak sides. After getting the information about the students' progress, participation in classes, their weak or strong sides, the teacher will be able to give them extra materials for improving their mistakes. Furthermore, this kind of method provides parents with an opportunity to control their children and their progress at school. By controlling the students' participation like this, the teachers can work effectively and conduct their lessons without any problem and the parents will be always aware of their children's education.

CONCLUSION

Artificial intelligence is making big changes in a lot of spheres nowadays, starting with education till medicine. By making learning more accessible from different

parts of the world, personalized, efficient, it gains more and more poverty and usage among students and teachers as well. If ai allows students to check their tasks and get feedback, the teachers may use it for checking homework and save up their time. The ai generated tools are helpful only if they are used by not only students, but also by everyone in a right way. Because ai is not perfect, someone for example can hack your account in get your personal information, or others may find wrong info on specific topic and so on. These and other concerns should be always taken into account before using them so the students can use them in a proper way.

We must also admit that ai is evolving and if now we still keep having lessons in a traditional way by just reading and memorizing, the tomorrow's classes won't be like this at all. Everything, including teaching methods, lesson structures and etc will be changed dramatically because of evolution of ai powered tools. That's why, if we want to study in modern classrooms, have lessons through the use of innovations, we should start working on ourselves, trying to use the ai only in a proper way and then we can create our own modern technology classrooms.

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